

The Impact of Sports Practice On Some Ethical Values in The University Community, female students of Boucherit Lachkham campus as a case study

Rebhia Bentireche¹, Elmehdi CHIKH², Ahmed Ali Chachou³

^{1,2,3}Institute of Physical Education and Sport, University of Lghouat (Algeria), cognitive and applied audio labs for sports training through multiple approaches .

¹r.bentireche@lagh-univ.dz , ²e.chikh@lagh-univ.dz, ³a.chachou@lagh-univ.dz

ARTICLE INFORMATION

Original Research Paper

Received : 15/07/2023

Accepted : 14/09/2023

Published : 01/12/2023

Keywords: sports practice;
ethical values; university
community

Abstract

This study attempts to identify the impact of sports practice on some ethical values in the university community. Using the descriptive approach, researchers distributed one questionnaire based on the following variables (responsibility, honesty, and truthfulness) to a population of 36 university female students. Researchers also divided into two samples of 18 students, the first one practicing sports while the other does not. After collecting and analyzing the data, the study concluded that practicing sports has a positive impact on developing ethical values in the university community.

Corresponding author: Full name,
e-mail: r.bentireche@lagh-univ.dz

1. Introduction

Sports practice is considered one of the pillars and methods the individual relies on in his daily life. This is due to its importance for the individual and society in understanding social life and acquiring skills and ethical values. Sports practice is an important way in developing psychological traits, relationships with others, and improving individual sports behavior. Therefore, we found that the majority of individuals who practice sports and their games and activities characterized by positive psychological and social personal characteristics. The participation of these individuals in sports creates active elements in their societies. (Iyad Abdul Karim al Azzawi and Marwan Abdul Majid Ibrahim, 2002, p. 61)

Charles Butcher believes that sports activity is that integrated part of public education. An experimental field was aimed at forming a decent citizen in terms of physical, mental, emotional, and emotional aspects. This is through types of physical activity, just as sports practice comprises aspects of selected physical activities that are performed for the purpose of benefits that accrue to the individual as a result of the practice of this activity. (Al-Bassiouni, 1992, p. 09).

In addition, sports practice at the university would contribute to the development of good manners and treatment. In addition to disciplining the behavior of students and enhancing their attitudes towards proper behavior, instilling values and ethics that society is satisfied with. It also contributes to the development of desirable trends, such as the student's pride in his religion, beliefs, and country, his values and ethics, and strives to develop them. On the one hand, it strengthens the relationship between the student and his colleagues, teachers, administrative staff, family, and society. Moreover, it enhances independence and self-confidence aspects and relying on it. Enhancing also taking responsibility through participating in suitable activities to his needs, abilities, and preferences. (Moustafa al Sayeh Mohammad, 2006, p. 77).

Since the university is the second environment for students, it functions as a factory for social life and education. Students spend a significant portion of their daily lives in this environment, where they receive diverse forms of education and knowledge. The university plays a crucial role in shaping students' personalities, fostering their attitudes and behaviors, and facilitating their interactions with the broader community. Alongside fostering personal responsibility towards oneself and those in their immediate surroundings, students also place great importance on engaging

in complementary activities, particularly sports activities. This emphasis on sports is due to its significant contributions to the development of physical, intellectual, and overall health aspects. The importance of sports practice at the university becomes evident through its impact on students' personality development, enabling them to achieve success in various areas such as health, academia, social interactions, and psychological well-being. This positive impact extends not only to individuals rather to whole the society.

1.1. Literature Review

(Abdel-Abbas Abdel-Razzaq Abboud, 2008) attempted to identify ethical traits among athletes and non-athletes. The study involved constructing a scale to assess the most significant ethical characteristics, as well as comparing athletes and non-athletes in terms of courage, honesty, honesty, and modesty. Furthermore, the study aimed to determine the extent to which participation in sporting activities and events contributes to the development of these traits. The researcher employed the descriptive survey method for the study. The research sample consisted of two groups: one for constructing the scale and another for applying the scale. The study sample included (60) university students, with (30) students engaged in sports and 30 non-practitioners. Additionally, an initial experiment was conducted on a sample of (10) students, with (5) students involved in sports and (5) non-practitioners. The sample size for the scientific transactions related to the scale was 14 students, and the scale was applied to a sample of (90) individuals. In summary, the results of the study states the following:

- There are significant differences in the ethical traits variable between athletes and non-athletes of Thi-Qar University students.
- There are no significant differences in courage, modesty, and truthfulness traits of athletes in the students of Thi-Qar University.
- There are no significant differences in the honesty traits of athletes in the students of Thi-Qar University.

Wissam Al-Din Al-Kilani, conducted a study aimed to examine the impact of sports practice on the preservation of ethical values previously acquired by athletes through their family and school experiences, and to compare these athletes with non-athletes. The researcher adopted a descriptive approach and selected a study sample of 318 students, divided into two groups: athletes and non-athletes. The researcher utilized the differential values scale developed by Jaber Abdel-Hamid, which categorized ethical values into traditional values (such as ethical values, self-reliance, success in work, and concern for the future) and liberal or empty values (including

courtship and friendship, keeping up with others, relativism in attitudes, and interest in the present). Additionally, sportsmanship was measured using the scale developed by Essam Al-Hilali. The study's findings concluded that engaging in sports activities assists students in maintaining and enhancing their pre-existing ethical values (Wissam Al-Din Al-Kilani, 1995).

More specifically, experimental studies indicate that CWI generates a series of physiological changes including, the reduction of core body temperature (Peiffer, Abbiss, Watson, Nosaka, & Laursen, 2009). Through this literature review, we assume that the response of the recovery indicators varies significantly depending on the type of CWI recovery protocol. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to compare the effects of two recovery protocols by CWI after a state of intense fatigue in young Handball players.

1.2. Statement of the problem

In light of these what mentioned previously, we must raise the following questions:

Are there statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in the development of some ethical values in the university community?

1.2.1. Sub-questions

1- Are there statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing responsibility in the university community?

2- Are there statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing honesty in the university community?

3- Are there statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing truthfulness in the university community?

1.2.2. Hypothesis

There are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in the development of some ethical values in the university community.

1.2.3. Sub-Hypothesizes

1- There are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing responsibility in the university community.

2- There are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing honesty in the university community.

3- There are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing truthfulness in the university community.

1.2.4. Objectives of the study

- Identifying whether there are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing responsibility in the university community or not.
- Identifying whether there are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing honesty in the university community or not.
- Identifying whether there are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing truthfulness in the university community or not.

1.2.1. Key terms

Sports practice:

-Terminologically: It is considered one of the finest forms of sports and one of the trends in human sports culture. It is the most organized and the most skillful of the other forms (Amin Hawalli, 1996, p. 32).

-Procedurally: It is considered an essential factor in preparing a good individual in terms of physical, mental, psychological and social aspects.

Ethical values:

-Terminologically: it is a set of standards, virtues, and ideals brought by Islam. This represents the hypothesis that we cannot directly observe. Rather, we can rely on it through the verbal expression of the individual by choosing one of the alternatives that represent a group of behavioral behaviors. This is the latter that the individual may take when he is exposed to a situation, whether in his educational or public life (Zagloul Muhammad Saad, 2005, p. 65).

-Procedurally: It is a set of values that athletes acquire through their engagement in various types of sports activities. These values manifest in their good behavior and interactions with others, as well as their ability to distance themselves from unethical values and bad behaviors.

University student: in this study, the term focuses on female students residing in the university residence in Bouchrit Lachkhem, located in Laghouat, across all disciplines during the academic season of 2022/2023.

University community: The University is an environment in which students reside during their studies. It functions as a social institution established by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, aiming to provide diverse social services to students who reside far from the university.

2. Method and Materials

3.1 Approach

This study follows the descriptive approach because the study applies the quantitative research.

3.2 Pilot study

The exploratory study aims to assure the validity of the tool and estimate its psychometric properties of validity and reliability. It also helps to know the various circumstances surrounding the application process. Based on this, before starting the field study, we carried out an exploratory study, the purpose of which was the following:

- Identify the field and the possibility of conducting this study.
- Examination of the students in order to collect the largest possible number of information by which they can address the general form presented.
- Identifying the suitability of the study tool phrases in terms of clarity.

The sample of the exploratory study included 36 female students residing in the university residence in Boucharit Lachkhem, in the state of Laghouat, divided into 18 female students practice sports activities while 18 students do not.

3.4 Field of the study

This study was conducted on female students in Boucharit Lachkam female campus, Laghouat province.

3.5 Timeframe

Researchers conducted this study in the academic year from March – May 2023.

3.6 Population and sample

The study population consisted of university female students from the female campus, Laghouat. As for the sample, we relied on a sample of 36 female students, 18 female students who practice sports; while other 18 female students who do not practice sports.

3.7 Variables of the study

3.7.1 Independent variables

In this study, sports practice is the independent variable.

3.7.2 Dependent variables

In this study, ethical values (responsibility, honesty, and truthfulness) are the dependent variables.

3.8 Data gathering tools

Based on scientific criteria and the previous studies, Researchers distributed one questionnaire to measure ethical values (contained 10 questions for each variable). Researchers used 3-point Likert scale (3 for always, 2 for sometimes, and 1 for never).

3.8 Scientific basis of the data tools

3.8.1 Credibility of the tool

We used the validity of the arbitrators (reviewers) as a tool to ensure that the questionnaire measures what was prepared for it, as we distributed the questionnaire to 05 professors from the Institute of Science and Technology of Physical and Sports Activities. Based on the observations and directions made by the arbitrators (reviewers), we made the amendments that most of the arbitrators agreed upon. Where some phrases were deleted and others were changed carefully taking into account the notes.

3.8.2 Application procedures of the tool

- Obtaining approval from the Director of (University Campus Boucherit Lachkhem) to conduct the research.

Distributing the study tool among the sample.

- After selecting the study sample, the tool was distributed to (38) female students, 18 female students practicing sports activities and 18 non-practicing sports activities.

-Lastly, researchers collected and analyzed data statistically.

The square root of the reliability coefficient is equal to 0.98 calculated by Cronbach's alpha.

3.9 Statistical tools

This study used the following statistical tools Arithmetic Mean, Simple Regression, and T.tests. Researchers analyzed the data by the SPSS software.

3. Analysis and discussion

3.1.1 The results of first hypothesis:

Table1. Shows the arithmetic values and the Standard deviation of dependent variable responsibility for the practitioners and the non-practitioners.

T.tests	practitioners		non-practitioners		t	df	Sig.	difference meaning
	standard deviation	arithmetic average	standard deviation	arithmetic average				
developing responsibility in the University community	26.167	1.855	19.83	2.915	10.030	34	0.05	true

It became clear to us through the table shown above that the values of (T) and the type of difference between practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities. After developing (responsibility) value in the university community for the sample of (38) students at the significance level of (0.05); where the results of the arithmetic mean for sports activities practices were estimated at (26.16); and a standard deviation (1.85). Meanwhile, the results of the arithmetic mean for practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities were estimated at (19.83); and a standard deviation (2.91).

By calculating the value of (T.test) whose calculated value was (10.03) at the degree of freedom (34); it is a statistically significant value. This is explained by the probability value (Sig = 0,000) because it is smaller than the level of statistical significance (0.05); therefore, There are differences between practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities in developing responsibility value of in the university community in favor of practices.

3.1.2 Discussing the results of first hypothesis

After the statistical treatment of the significance of the difference between the degrees of developing responsibility value for the practitioners and the non-practitioners female students in sports activities. The results of the study indicated that there are statistically significant differences between the practitioners and the non-practitioners female students of sports activities in

the degree of the value of responsibility. This is shown in Table1. To conclude, sports activity raises students' self-confidence and proves their ability to contribute effectively. Whether through individual or group sports activities. Individual sports activities often allow female students to show their level of performance. However, considering that university institutions include a number of female students who are distinguished by vast individual differences, the activity presented is not an end in itself as much as it is a means to achieve educational and moral goals. In the sense that the numerical score obtained by female students in games and competitions is not important compared to the importance of developing and developing their personal abilities, and addressing some psychological problems such as lack of confidence in their abilities. Enhancing the students' sense of their abilities and relying on them to add to the team. It also helps a lot in consolidating her relationships with her classmates. Which makes them feel responsible and that they are an effective element among their female colleagues. Based on these findings, it is evident that there are statistically significant differences between practitioners and the non-practitioners female students in the university community involvement in developing responsibility value.

3.2.1 The results of second hypothesis

Table2. Shows the arithmetic values and the Standard deviation of dependent variable honesty for the practitioners and the non-practitioners.

T.tests	practitioners		non-practitioners		t	df	Sig.	difference meaning
	standard deviation	arithmetic average	standard deviation	arithmetic average				
developing honesty in the University community	27.50	2.148	21.056	2.979	9.512	34	0.05	true

Table2. shows that the values of (T) and the type of difference between practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities. After developing (honesty) value in the university community for the sample of (38) students at the significance level of (0.05); where the results of the arithmetic mean for sports activities practices were estimated at (27.50); and a standard deviation (2.14). Meanwhile, the results of the arithmetic mean for

practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities were estimated at (21.05); and a standard deviation (2.97).

By calculating the value of (T.test) whose calculated value was (9.51) at the degree of freedom (34); it is a statistically significant value. This is explained by the probability value (Sig=0,000) because it is smaller than the level of statistical significance (0.05); therefore, There are differences between practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities in developing (honesty) value of in the university community in favor of practices.

3.2.2 Discussing the results of first hypothesis

After the statistical treatment of the significance of the difference between the degrees of developing honesty value for the practitioners and the non-practitioners female students in sports activities. The results of the study indicated that there are statistically significant differences between the practitioners and the non-practitioners female students of sports activities in the degree of the value of honesty. This is shown in Table2.

In conclusion, that the practitioner students of sports activity outperformed the non-practitioners. When the athlete is honest with himself in his actions, this feature will be reflected on the group of students and will be reflected on the segments of society for sports activities. Because they are synonyms and an important tool in acquiring noble moral qualities and characteristics, and this was confirmed by (Abdul Abbas Abdul Razzaq Abboud. 2008. p. 181). We must focus on honesty because it is an essential feature and pillar in the system of ethics and sports principles. Therefore, the athlete must be an example and a role model for others to change our society's view of those who practice sports activities in a positive way.

3.3.1 The results of third hypothesis

Table3. Shows the arithmetic values and the Standard deviation of dependent variable (truthfulness) for the practitioners and the non-practitioners.

T.tests	practitioners			non-practitioners			t	df	Sig.	difference meaning
	n	standard deviatio	average	n	standard deviatio	average				
developing truthfulness in the University community		28.111	1.811		22.111	2.987	12.369	34	0.05	true

Table 3. shows that the values of (T) and the type of difference between practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities. After developing truthfulness value in the university community for the sample of (38) students at the significance level of (0.05); where the results of the arithmetic mean for sports activities practices were estimated at (28.11); and a standard deviation (1.81). Meanwhile, the results of the arithmetic mean for practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities were estimated at (22.11); and a standard deviation (2.98).

By calculating the value of (T.test) whose calculated value was (9.51) at the degree of freedom (34); it is a statistically significant value. This is explained by the probability value (Sig=0,000) because it is smaller than the level of statistical significance (0.05); therefore, There are differences between practitioners and the non-practitioners of sports activities in developing (truthfulness) value of in the university community in favor of practices.

3.3.2 Discussing the results of first hypothesis:

After the statistical treatment of the significance of the difference between the degrees of developing truthfulness value for the practitioners and the non-practitioners female students in sports activities. The results of the study indicated that there are statistically significant differences between the practitioners and the non-practitioners female students of sports activities in the degree of the value of truthfulness. This is shown in Table3.

In conclusion, female students who practice sports outperformed female students who do not, indicating that sports have an impact on the behavior

and actions of students. A truthful individual is respected and appreciated by all. The truthfulness that we need in physical and sports activities is truthful in dealing (Jasim 2012,712). This is what (Abdul Karim Imani. 2009. p. 287) concluded that truthfulness is one of the greatest human qualities and the highest moral virtues. It is one of the most important foundations in building society and the happiness of the nation. As it is associated with every matter of life and every interest of society. Since truthfulness is the conformity of the saying with the external reality, it leaves tangible and direct effects on the life of the individual and society.

4. Conclusion

Taking everything into account, our study on sports practice and its impact on some of the ethical values in the university community, we have gained some insights. Presenting, analyzing, and interpreting the results of the ethical values questionnaire after the distribution of the questionnaire.

Ending with discussing them in the light of research hypotheses and previous studies. We concluded that sports activities contribute to achieving ethical values among students. We also found that female students who practice sports are more self-directed, and as a result, have more ability to direct their behavior on their own. Furthermore, they are more responsible and aware of their value and freedom; in addition, they have better social skills and are more helpful, peaceful, non-violent, and fair in their behavior and dealings. Where they feel mutual appreciation and respect from others. Finally, the ability to establish effective friendships with others. All of these things contribute greatly to helping students at this stage enhance their ethical values.

Based on what we mentioned above, we can confirm the following important points:

- ✓ There are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing responsibility in the university community.
- ✓ There are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing honesty in the university community.
- ✓ There are statistically significant differences between the practicing and non-practicing female students of sports activities in developing truthfulness in the university community.

- ✓ Sport activities contribute to the ethical values of female student in the university community

Overall, we can say that sports practice has several positive effects in developing the individual's behavior his good relationship with society.

5. Suggestions

In light of the results obtained regarding our research, we decided to present some suggestions and recommendations. We hope these will be taken into consideration, and we have summarized them as follows:

- Encouraging sports practice and ensuring its essence with ethical values, mutual respect, and forming relationships.
- The need to pay attention to moral values, especially for students who participate in sports activities.
- The need to provide suitable places for practicing sports in residences, such as stadiums, halls, etc.
- Developing and strengthening students' attitudes toward sports in order to reach a very positive level in all fields
- The need to increase interest in sports and to encourage students to practice them.
- Organizing more sports activities and gatherings that enhance social relations among students
- Increasing interest in athletes and making sports practice a modification and refinement of behavior.

6. Bibliography list

Books: author, title, publishing house, year.

- Oussama El khairi, Scientific Research Methods (first edition), Al-Raya House for Publishing and Distribution Jordan, 2016.
- Amin Anwar Khouli, Sports and society, Kuwait, The National Council for Literature and the Arts, 1996.
- Iyad Abdul Karim al Azzawi. And Marwan Abdel Majeed Ibrahim, Sociology of Educational and Mathematical Education. Oman. Scientific House and Culture House for publication and distribution, 2002.
- Bashir Krum, The Role of Practicing Physical and Sports Activities in Developing Some Moral Values, Journal of Sports Creativity, Issue 18, p. 58-72.
- Jawdat Ezzat Atwi. Scientific research methods, concepts, tools, and statistical methods. Jordan, 5th edition. House of Culture, 2015.
- Khaled scientific research methodology, Algeria, Rehana Publishing House, 2003.
- Zaghoul Mohamed Saad, Value-Oriented Physical Education Curricula in Confronting the Reflections of the Era of Globalization, first edition, Cairo. Book Center for Publishing, 2005.
- Abdel-Abbas Abdel-Razzaq Abboud, Ethical characteristics between athletes and non-athletes. Dhi Qar University Journal. Volume 6, Issue 2008, p. 170-187.
- Muhammad Awad Al-Basiouni.. Theories and methods of physical and sports education. Edition 2. Algeria. Algerian Publications Office. 1992.
- Mustafa Sayeh Mohamed., Sports Sociology in Physical Education, Alexandria, Dar Al-Wafaa, our printing and publishing house. 2006.